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Article in *Revista de Gestão Social e Ambiental* · January 2025

DOI: 10.24857/rgsa.v19n1-107

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CFD SIMULATIONS FOR FILTER LAYER OPTIMIZATION: SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF FLOW VELOCITY, PARTICLE SIZE, ROUGHNESS, AND PARTICLE RATE

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The objective of this study is to examine the sensitivity of particle retention processes in artificial porous media to variations in fluid injection velocity, particle size, injection rate, and surface roughness. Similarly, this investigation contributes to the understanding of the mechanisms governing particle transport and retention, as well as supports the optimization of filtration systems across various applications.

Theoretical Framework: The research builds upon the established theories of porous media flow, particle transport, and interfacial phenomena, particularly focusing on the application of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations to the study of particulate matter retention in water.

Method: In this work, a sensitivity analysis was conducted using a computational model implemented in ANSYS-CFX software, which allows for the study of water-particle mixture percolation in artificial porous media. The main parameters analyzed included flow velocity, particle size, surface roughness, and injection rate. Prior to simulations, X-ray computed tomography (μ CT-XR) was employed to obtain detailed geometric information of the porous media, which was used to generate realistic computational models.

Results and Discussion: The results obtained revealed particle retention in porous media is influenced by flow velocity, particle size, and media roughness. Higher velocities and larger particles promote deposition. In the discussion section, these results are contextualized in light of the theoretical framework, highlighting the implications and relationships identified. Possible discrepancies and limitations of the study are also considered in this section.

Research Implications: These findings provide valuable insights to understand the limits of applicability of computational CFD when applied to the optimization of barrier and filter construction which have significant implications for various applications, such as water filtration, soil contamination, and reservoir engineering.

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Originality/Value: This study contributes to the literature by providing valuable insights about key factors influencing particle retention. The relevance and value of this research are evident in the potential application of CFD simulations, which, through sensitivity analyses, provide valuable understanding about optimizing filter design and mitigating water contamination.

Keywords: Particle Retention, Water Filtration, Surface Deposition, Pollutant Transport, Poured Media, Zirconia Particle.

SIMULAÇÕES CFD PARA OTIMIZAÇÃO DE CAMADAS FILTRANTES: ANÁLISE DE SENSIBILIDADE DA VELOCIDADE DO FLUXO, TAMANHO DE PARTÍCULA, RUGOSIDADE E TAXA DE INJEÇÃO DE PARTÍCULAS

RESUMO

Objetivo: O objetivo deste estudo é examinar a sensibilidade dos processos de retenção de partículas em meios porosos artificiais a variações na velocidade de injeção de fluido, tamanho das partículas, taxa de injeção e rugosidade da superfície. Da mesma forma, esta investigação contribui para a compreensão dos mecanismos que governam o transporte e a retenção de partículas, bem como suporta a otimização de sistemas de filtração em diversas aplicações.

Referencial Teórico: A pesquisa se baseia nas teorias estabelecidas de escoamento em meios porosos, transporte de partículas e fenômenos interfaciais, com foco particular na aplicação de simulações de Fluidodinâmica Computacional (CFD) ao estudo da retenção de material particulado em água.

Método: Neste trabalho, uma análise de sensibilidade foi conduzida utilizando um modelo computacional implementado no software ANSYS-CFX, que permite o estudo da percolação da mistura água-partícula em meios porosos artificiais. Os principais parâmetros analisados incluíram velocidade do fluxo, tamanho das partículas, rugosidade da superfície e taxa de injeção. Antes das simulações, tomografia computadorizada de raios-X (μ CT-XR) foi empregada para obter informações geométricas detalhadas dos meios porosos, que foram utilizadas para gerar modelos computacionais realistas.

Resultados e Discussão: Os resultados obtidos revelaram que a retenção de partículas em meios porosos é influenciada pela velocidade do fluxo, tamanho de partícula e rugosidade do meio. Velocidades mais altas e partículas maiores favorecem a deposição. Na seção de discussão, esses resultados são contextualizados à luz do referencial teórico, destacando as implicações e relações identificadas. Possíveis discrepâncias e limitações do estudo também são consideradas nesta seção.

Implicações da Pesquisa: Esses resultados fornecem insights valiosos para compreender os limites de aplicabilidade das simulações de CFD quando aplicadas à otimização de barreiras e construção de filtros, o que tem implicações significativas para diversas aplicações, como filtração de água, contaminação do solo e engenharia de reservatórios.

Originalidade/Valor: Este estudo contribui para a literatura ao fornecer insights valiosos sobre os principais fatores que influenciam a retenção de partículas. A relevância e o valor desta pesquisa são evidenciados pela apresentação de simulações de CFD, que, através de análises de sensibilidade, fornecem um valioso entendimento sobre a otimização do projeto de filtros e a mitigação da contaminação da água.

Palavras-chave: Retenção de Partículas, Filtração de Água, Deposição Superficial, Transporte de Poluentes, Meios Porosos, Partícula de Zircônia.

SIMULACIONES CFD PARA LA OPTIMIZACIÓN DE ESTRATOS FILTRANTES: ANÁLISIS DE SENSIBILIDAD DE LA VELOCIDAD DEL FLUJO, TAMAÑO DE PARTÍCULA, RUGOSIDAD Y TASA DE PARTÍCULAS

RESUMEN

Objetivo: El objetivo de este estudio es examinar la sensibilidad de los procesos de retención de partículas en medios porosos artificiales a variaciones en la velocidad de inyección de fluido, tamaño de partículas, tasa de

inyección y rugosidad superficial. De igual manera, esta investigación contribuye a la comprensión de los mecanismos que gobiernan el transporte y la retención de partículas, así como apoya la optimización de sistemas de filtración en diversas aplicaciones.

Marco Teórico: La investigación se basa en las teorías establecidas de flujo en medios porosos, transporte de partículas y fenómenos interfaciales, con un enfoque particular en la aplicación de simulaciones de Dinámica de Fluidos Computacional (CFD) al estudio de la retención de material particulado en agua.

Método: En este trabajo, se realizó un análisis de sensibilidad utilizando un modelo computacional implementado en el software ANSYS-CFX, que permite el estudio de la percolación de la mezcla agua-partícula en medios porosos artificiales. Los principales parámetros analizados incluyeron velocidad del flujo, tamaño de partículas, rugosidad superficial y tasa de inyección. Antes de las simulaciones, se empleó tomografía computarizada de rayos X (μ CT-XR) para obtener información geométrica detallada de los medios porosos, la cual se utilizó para generar modelos computacionales realistas.

Resultados y Discusión: Los resultados obtenidos revelaron que la retención de partículas en medios porosos está influenciada por la velocidad del flujo, el tamaño de partícula y la rugosidad del medio. Velocidades más altas y partículas más grandes favorecen la deposición. En la sección de discusión, estos resultados se contextualizan a la luz del marco teórico, destacando las implicaciones y relaciones identificadas. También se consideran posibles discrepancias y limitaciones del estudio en esta sección.

Implicaciones de la Investigación: Estos resultados proporcionan valiosos conocimientos para comprender los límites de aplicabilidad de las simulaciones de CFD cuando se aplican a la optimización de barreras y construcción de filtros, lo que tiene implicaciones significativas para diversas aplicaciones, como la filtración de agua, la contaminación del suelo y la ingeniería de reservorios.

Originalidad/Valor: Este estudio contribuye a la literatura proporcionando valiosos conocimientos sobre los factores clave que influyen en la retención de partículas. La relevancia y el valor de esta investigación se evidencian por la presentación de simulaciones de CFD como herramienta para optimizar filtros y barreras reactivas permeables en la prevención y remediación de la contaminación de recursos hídricos.

Palabras clave: Retención de Partículas, Filtración de Agua, Deposición Superficial, Transporte de Contaminantes, Medios Porosos, Partícula de Zirconio.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Understanding particle movement through porous media is fundamental for ensuring water quality, managing water resources, optimizing industrial processes, and preventing soil contamination. The transport of water and pollutants in porous media is governed by the principles of hydrodynamics and hydrology (Frippiat & Holeyman, 2008; Lee & Jung, 2022). In essence, porous media consist of a solid matrix (e.g., soil, rock) with void spaces between the particles, called pores (Ling *et al.*, 2021; Leal *et al.*, 2023). Water and pollutants can move within these pores through physical and chemical processes, which depend primarily on the

characteristics of the porous medium and the properties of the water and pollutants (Nielsen *et al.*, 1997).

In this context, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations play a crucial role in analyzing particle transport and retention processes in porous media (Tu *et al.*, 2013). These simulations allow for a detailed analysis of fluid and particle behavior, considering input parameters such as flow velocity, particle size and injection rate, and surface characteristics of the porous medium (Tu *et al.*, 2013; Afzali *et al.*, 2022; Li, *et al.*, 2023). By providing insights into flow patterns and microscopic interactions in particle retention within porous media, CFD simulations contribute to optimizing engineering designs, remediation strategies, and industrial process improvements, resulting in significant advancements in research and development (Tu *et al.*, 2013; Afzali *et al.*, 2022; Li *et al.*, 2023; Elrahmani *et al.*, 2023).

Some studies on particle retention in porous media using CFD simulation approaches can be found in the literature, among which Sadeghnejad *et al.* (2022) investigated the clogging of porous structures using CFD simulations. Applying the Euler-Lagrange approach, the authors observed that particle size and adhesion forces exert a predominant influence on permeability through clogging mechanisms, rather than surface deposition. They also highlighted that particle retention reaches its maximum at a critical velocity. This study, being one of the most recent in this area, opens up a range of questions regarding the sensitivity of particle retention processes to variations in input parameters.

The present study aims to investigate the sensitivity of particle retention processes in artificial porous media composed of glass beads to variations in the input parameters of fluid injection velocity, particle size and injection rate, and surface roughness of the glass beads.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to Nielsen *et al.*, 1997, porous media are composed of a solid matrix (e.g., soil, rock) with void spaces between the particles, termed pores. Water and pollutants can migrate within these pores through physical and chemical processes, primarily dependent on the characteristics of the porous medium and the properties of the water and pollutants.

Water transport through porous media is referred to as porous flow. This process involves the passage of water through pores and channels under the influence of hydraulic pressure gradients. Hydraulic pressure is a measure of the energy associated with water, dependent on the height of the water column above a reference point and its properties. Water

flows from a high-pressure point to a low-pressure point, following the laws of fluid motion, such as Darcy's law and the Navier-Stokes equations (Nielsen *et al.*, 1997; Hariti *et al.*, 2020).

Darcy's law states that the flow of water through a porous medium is directly proportional to the permeability of the porous medium, and inversely proportional to the hydraulic pressure gradient and viscosity of water. Therefore, the greater the hydraulic pressure difference between two points in the porous medium, the greater the flow between them, provided that the medium is sufficiently permeable to allow the fluid to pass more easily (Wang *et al.*, 2022). This permeability depends on the characteristics of the solid matrix and the void spaces between the particles of the medium (Nielsen *et al.*, 1997; Guha, 2008; White, 2009; Hariti *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2022).

Two primary mechanisms govern the transport of suspended particles in porous media: advection and diffusion (Bear, 1988; Sahimi, 1995). The interplay of these mechanisms determines the transport pattern of suspended particles in porous media. The complexity of this transport is influenced by the characteristics of the porous medium, as well as the properties of the suspended particles (such as size, shape, and charge) and the flow conditions of the water (such as velocity and direction) (McDowell-Boyer *et al.*, 1986; Bear, 1988; Sahimi, 1995; Deng *et al.*, 2022).

Advection refers to the transport of suspended particles along with the flow of water through the porous medium. This transport occurs due to the velocity differences between the water and the particles, and as the water flows through the pores of the material, it drags the suspended particles in its direction, similar to the transport of objects carried by river currents (McDowell-Boyer *et al.*, 1986; Bear, 1988; Sahimi, 1995; Deng *et al.*, 2022; Monga *et al.*, 2023). The diffusion occurs due to the random motion of suspended particles, resulting in their spreading in all directions. Diffusion is particularly significant for small particles, which are more affected by thermal motion and collisions with other particles and water molecules. Diffusion tends to spread suspended particles throughout the porous medium (Bear, 1988; Sahimi, 1995; Deng *et al.*, 2022; Ren *et al.*, 2022; Monga *et al.*, 2023).

Filter layers are designed to remove unwanted particles and impurities from water, allowing only clean water to pass through the pores. According to Nan *et al.* (2023), various hydrodynamic and physicochemical processes play a crucial role in generating retained particles in porous media, both saturated and unsaturated. The main mechanisms governing particle retention are surface deposition, clogging, and sieving.

Surface forces, such as van der Waals and electrostatic forces, are responsible for the adhesion and agglomeration of particles on the matrix surface. Clogging occurs when multiple

particles form a bridge or arch at the pore throats. Sieving occurs when particles block pore throats that are smaller than their diameters. These mechanisms are illustrated in Figure 1. Factors such as flow velocity, initial particle concentration, particle size and polydispersity, ionic strength, and surface heterogeneity (roughness and wettability) govern the magnitude of particle retention in porous media (Lin *et al.*, 2021; Sadeghnejad *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 1

Processes of particle retention in porous media.

Source: YE *et al.*, 2019. Mechanism of Suspended Kaolinite Particle Clogging in Porous Media During Managed Aquifer Recharge. *Groundwater*, v. 57, n. 5, 2019.

CFD simulation is a numerical technique used to model and analyze the behavior of fluids, such as liquids and gases, and their interactions with solid structures (Tu *et al.*, 2013). It allows for the solution of the fundamental equations governing fluid motion, such as the conservation equations of mass, momentum, and energy, using computational methods to predict flow behavior under different conditions (Tu *et al.*, 2013; Spurin *et al.*, 2023; Zheng *et al.*, 2023).

This approach offers several advantages, including cost savings, as it eliminates the need for physical experiments, reducing the costs associated with building models and laboratory testing. Additionally, it provides flexibility to simulate a wide range of conditions and scenarios, enabling a more comprehensive analysis of fluid behavior under different boundary conditions, geometries, and operating parameters. The speed of obtaining results is another advantage, as simulations can be run on high-performance computers, accelerating the design and optimization process of fluid dynamic systems (Tu *et al.*, 2013; Sadeghnejad *et al.*, 2022; Nan *et al.*, 2023; Dhar *et al.*, 2024).

In the current context, the importance of CFD simulations in studying transport phenomena and particle retention in porous media is emphasized (Tu *et al.*, 2013). These

simulations enable a thorough analysis of fluid and particle behavior, considering variables such as flow velocity and porous media geometry (Tu *et al.*, 2013; Afzali *et al.*, 2022; Li *et al.*, 2023). By providing insights into flow patterns and microscopic interactions during particle retention in porous media, they contribute to the optimization of engineering designs, remediation strategies, and industrial process improvements, resulting in substantial advancements in research and development. For this purpose, mass, energy and momentum balance equations are calculated for each particle throughout its trajectory in the medium. (Tu *et al.*, 2013; Afzali *et al.*, 2022; Li *et al.*, 2023; Elrahmani *et al.*, 2023).

3 METHODOLOGY

For this study, three artificial porous media, referred to as reference columns, were constructed and scanned using X-rays micro-CT (μ CT-XR) to generate a representative geometric model. These models were then meshed to enable simulations. Standard conditions of velocity, particle size, particle rate, and porous media surface roughness were established for the simulations, and these were then varied to study sensitivity. Each of these methodological steps is better described in the subsequent subtopics. Building upon the previous work of Silva *et al.* (2024), this study extends the investigation into porous media applied to filtration systems.

The reference columns were assembled in an acrylic cylinder using glass pebbles as a solid matrix. The regular surface of glass pebbles ensures that, as they have well-defined and connected voids, the medium presents absolute porosity equal to the effective porosity, important for porosimetry methods based on column saturation. Of the three constructed reference columns, one was filled with 3 mm pebbles (CF3), another with 4 mm pebbles (CF4), and the third was filled with a 50:50 volumetric mixture of 3 mm and 4 mm pebbles (CFM). The reference columns are shown in Figure 2. The reference columns CF3, CF4, and CFM exhibited porosities of 37.14%, 39.51%, and 37.55%, respectively. These porosity values were obtained from helium gas porosimetry measurements as reported in Silva *et al.* (2024).

Figure 2

Studied reference columns.

Tomographic images were acquired using a third-generation μ CT-XR system, model NIKON XT H 225 ST. These images were obtained based on the attenuation of X-ray beams incident on a sample located between the source and the detector. The scanning conditions were as follows: voltage of 200 kV, current of 90 μ A, a 0.5 mm Copper (Cu) filter, and a resolution of 25 μ m. Tomographic projections were reconstructed using the CTPro 3D XT 3.03 software (Nikon Metrology, 2015).

The initial stage of the geometric model generation process involves the reconstruction of tomographic images and subsequent extraction of surfaces to form a three-dimensional (3D) model in STL format, facilitated by the 3D Viewer plugin within the ImageJ 1.54f software (Ferreira and Rasband, 2012). STL files encode geometric data by defining surfaces through triangular facets. Each facet is characterized by a unit normal vector, orthogonal to its corresponding triangle with a magnitude of 1.0, and delineated by the coordinates of its three vertices. Hence, for every facet, a total of 12 numerical values are stored: three for the normal vector and nine for the coordinates of the vertices (Szilvsi-Nagy and Mátyási, 2003). This representation ensures the accurate preservation of surface topology and geometric details essential for subsequent computational analyses and simulations.

As an additional benefit, this file format can be loaded into the Ansys Discovery SpaceClaim software (ANSYS, 2023). Using the latter, the model with triangular facets is transformed into a solid body (Figure 3a). Following this transformation, repair tools are applied to identify gaps, missing faces, extra or duplicated edges, among other issues in the solid body. Finally, the glass bead column is enclosed within a cylinder with dimensions equivalent to those of the inner wall of the PVC column, and a Boolean subtraction operation

is performed between the cylinder and the beads. The resulting solid body (Figure 3b) from this subtraction operation corresponds to the void space through which the fluid will flow, and it is this solid body that should be meshed and used for simulations with Ansys CFX. The process of generating this geometry is repeated identically for the three reference columns.

Figure 3

Solid body representation of the glass bead column (a) and fluid region after Boolean subtraction operation (b).

The next step involved generating tetrahedral element meshes for the geometrical model. Mesh quality parameters, such as Skewness and Orthogonal Quality, were evaluated to ensure they remained within acceptable thresholds, thereby ensuring the robustness and accuracy of the computational analysis. A mesh independence study was conducted to ascertain the element size at which the results remain unaffected by the mesh resolution. Different mesh element sizes, ranging from 0.50 mm to 0.25 mm, were evaluated. Previous experience was used to select a range of mesh element sizes that were close to the size at which the result becomes independent of the mesh. Table 1 presents the sizes of elements studied and the corresponding numbers of nodes and elements generated for each mesh in the geometric model of CF3.

Table 1

Characteristics of the studied meshes.

Mesh ID	Element size (mm)	Elements	Nodes
1	0.50	2.24M	665k
2	0.45	2.45M	700k
3	0.40	2.75M	751k
4	0.35	3.19M	827k
5	0.30	3.90M	951k
6	0.25	5.03M	1.15M

To assess mesh independence, transient calculations of 100 seconds were conducted with each mesh, evaluating the convergence of the average quantity of particles exiting the computational domain through the outlet at each time step (set to 0.25 seconds). Figure 4 illustrates the values obtained for this parameter for each mesh. As observed, the results are quite close to each other, as the mesh element sizes were intentionally chosen close to the value where results become independent of the mesh. Upon evaluating the convergence of this parameter, it was found to converge below a relative difference of 1% starting from mesh 2 (element size 0.45 cm) and onwards. Therefore, all simulations with ANSYS CFX will be conducted using that element size.

Figure 4

Particles retained on the computational domain across studied meshes.

The simulations employing the Euler-Lagrange approach, were conducted transiently using the ANSYS CFX 2023R1 code (ANSYS, 2023), with a total duration of 100 seconds and time steps of 0.25 seconds. Zirconia particles were used to compose the percolated suspension, with different diameters being set for sensitivity analysis. The temperature of the water-particle mixture was set as isothermal and maintained at 25°C. Turbulence effects were neglected, and the laminar model was utilized. By employing the Euler-Lagrange approach, which models

particles discretely and the fluid as a continuum, we can accurately capture fluid-particle interaction phenomena within the system. A no-slip boundary condition was applied to the rigid walls of both the PVC column and the glass beads.

One-Way fluid-particle interaction modeling was used, considering that comparison with the fully-coupled model revealed differences below 0.5% for the average quantity of deposited particles, while the required computation time was 10% of that of the other model.

The buoyancy model was employed, with gravity acting against the motion of the mixture (Figure 5). To simulate the outflow from the column, an 'opening' boundary condition was established at the exit. This condition allows fluid and particles to exit freely from the computational domain. The surface tension coefficient of water was utilized, and the Schiller Naumann model was employed for drag force calculations. A residual target for the root mean square (RMS) was set at 10^{-6} . Additionally, the High Resolution and Second Order Backward Euler models were employed for advection and transient schemes, respectively.

Figure 5

Computational model in Ansys CFX.

Material properties for water and zirconia particles were configured according to the ANSYS CFX 2023R1 (ANSYS, 2023) material library. A restitution coefficient of 0.9 was assigned to the glass bead wall. An inlet velocity of 1.0 mm/s was set for the mixture, with 10 μm particles, and no roughness was assumed on the glass bead wall. A particle inlet rate equivalent to 2.0×10^4 particles per second was initially established as the standard case for mesh independence analysis. These parameters were subsequently examined in sensitivity studies.

Sensitivity analyses were conducted on four parameters. For the velocity sensitivity study, five velocity values (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 mm/s) were investigated. Particle size sensitivity analysis included five different sizes ranging from 5 to 25 μm , with increments of 5

μm between each point. Glass bead wall roughness sensitivity was explored using the Sommerfeld-Frank model, with assumed values of 5, 10, 15, and 20 μm for both the length and height of the roughness. Lastly, sensitivity analysis on the particle inlet rate examined values of 5.0×10^3 , 1.0×10^4 , 1.5×10^4 , and 2.0×10^4 particles per second.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study investigated how various factors influence pore blockage in porous media, a phenomenon known as clogging. By varying flow velocity, particle size, surface roughness, and particle injection rate, we assessed their impacts on the rate and extent of particle retention. Beforehand, preferential flow paths were observed in the studied media that matched the positions of the fractions deposited in the medium, and were unaffected by variations in velocity, size, roughness, and particle rate parameters. This relationship is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6

Fluid paths and volume fraction of zirconia particles on the surface of the reference columns CF3 ((a) e (b)), CF4 ((c) e (d)) e CFM ((e) e (f)).

The identification of preferential flow paths within filter beds holds significant promise for predicting potential failure points, thus facilitating proactive optimization. For example, by anticipating regions most prone to clogging in permeable reactive barriers employed for aquifer contamination prevention or remediation, substantial costs associated with barrier replacement can be averted. Moreover, a comprehensive understanding of particle deposition and retention rates within filters can enable accurate estimation of equipment lifespan, mitigating the wasteful consumption of reclaimed or purified water.

Regarding the influence of the parameters studied in this work, the results presented in Figure 7 showed that particle retention in the studied medium is inversely proportional to the velocity established for the simulation, as previously indicated by the theory. This phenomenon can be attributed to the fact that, by holding particle mass and size constant and varying only the flow velocity, the sole parameter affected is the kinetic energy with which particles impact or approach the porous medium surface. Consequently, as the kinetic energy (velocity) of zirconia particles impinging upon the glass beads diminishes, the probability of these particles adhering to the surface through adhesive interactions is enhanced.

Figure 7

Particle retention graph in reference columns CF3 (a), CF4 (b) and CFM (c) from the fluid injection velocities variation.

The simulations also showed to be sensitive to particle size (Figure 8). Despite the small inherent differences in the porous matrix characteristics of each sample, it can be observed that 5 μm and 20 μm particles are less retained in all studied reference columns. The higher retention rate observed for intermediate-sized particles (10 μm and 15 μm) suggests that two factors may be at play: (1) 5 μm particles are very light and easily carried away by the flow, decreasing their adhesion to the porous surface; (2) due to the radius-to-mass ratio of spheres, 20 μm particles have a mass 16 times greater when compared to 5 μm particles, which can decrease the particle's adhesion to the porous surface.

While a correlation between particle retention and media porosity is often observed, it is not applicable in this case. The large size of the glass beads composing the reference columns (millimeter scale) results in pore throats too large to effectively retain the zirconia particles.

Consequently, particle retention is primarily attributed to adhesive forces, which are influenced by particle mass and velocity. Altering particle size affects both these parameters, with extremes (lower velocity with higher mass and vice versa) significantly impacting retention. The higher retention of 15 μm particles suggests that their specific mass-volume-diameter ratio enhances adhesive interactions within the porous medium.

Figure 8

Particle retention graph in reference columns CF3 (a), CF4 (b) and CFM (c) from the zirconia particle size variation.

In contrast to what has been observed so far, roughness (Figure 9) did not present significant alterations to establish a dependency relationship with the particle retention rate, while it is clear that increasing surface roughness can directly impact particle retention. Although the results do not indicate a significant sensitivity of the CFD simulations to this

parameter, it is premature to conclude that there is no sensitivity. Therefore, further studies are warranted. This includes increasing the range of input values as well as investigating the impact of particle sizes on different surface roughness.

Figure 9

Particle retention graph in reference columns CF3 (a), CF4 (b) and CFM (c) from the surface roughness variation.

Finally, the particle rate (Figure 10) showed a direct proportionality in zirconia retention, similar to the relationship observed in the variation of velocities. The sensitivity to this parameter is linked to the pattern whereby the more particles are injected into the medium, the more particles are retained. An additional factor contributing to this behavior is particle-particle retention, wherein particles adhering to the porous matrix walls can act as nucleation sites for further particle deposition, forming filter cakes. The agglomeration of these filter cakes

can subsequently obstruct pore throats, leading to the retention of additional particles via a clogging mechanism (inner blocking showed in Figure 1).

Figure 10

Particle retention graph in reference columns CF3 (a), CF4 (b) and CFM (c) from the particle injection rate variation.

5 CONCLUSION

The study observed the factors influencing particle retention (clogging) within porous media. Our findings demonstrate that: (1) particle retention decreases with increasing flow velocity, as predicted by theoretical models, (2) both very small ($5\ \mu\text{m}$) and very large ($20\ \mu\text{m}$) particles exhibit lower retention rates compared to intermediate sizes. This could be attributed to factors such as low inertia for smaller particles and increased mass and potential for bridging for larger particles, (3) surprisingly, surface roughness did not significantly influence particle

retention in this study, (4) increasing the particle injection rate directly correlates with increased particle retention.

Furthermore, the study observed preferential flow paths within the porous media that remain consistent despite variations in simulation parameters. These findings provide valuable insights to understand the limits of applicability of computational fluid dynamics simulations when applied to the optimization of barrier and filter construction which have significant implications for various applications, such as water filtration, soil contamination, and reservoir engineering.

This study provides a foundational understanding of the factors influencing clogging. Further research could explore the combined effects of these factors, investigate the impact of different particle shapes and distributions, and refine the understanding of preferential flow paths and their influence on clogging dynamics and the filter life-time.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was partially supported by the Fundação de Amparo à Ciência e Tecnologia de Pernambuco (FACEPE), project numbers: IBPG-1064-3.09/22 and BFP-0146-3.09/23 and the Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq), project number: 465764/2014-2 Observatório Nacional da Dinâmica da Água e de Carbono no Bioma Caatinga (ONDACBC). The authors also acknowledge CNPq for supporting this research through the Productivity Fellowship granted to Antonio Celso Dantas Antonino.

REFERENCES

- Afzali, S., Rezaei, N., Zendejboudi, S., Chatzis, I. (2022). Computational fluid dynamic simulation of multi-phase flow in fractured porous media during water-alternating-gas injection process. *Journal of Hydrology*, 610, 127852.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2022.127852>
- Ansys, Team. (2023). Ansys CFX-Solver Theory Guide, *Release 2023 R1*. ANSYS, Inc., 2023b.
- Bear, J. (1988). *Dynamics of fluids in porous media*. New York: Dover.
- Deng, H., Gharasoo, M., Zhang, L., Dai, Z., Hajizadeh, A., Peters, C. A., Soullaine, C., Thullner, M., Cappellen, P. V. (2022). A perspective on applied geochemistry in porous media: Reactive transport modeling of geochemical dynamics and the interplay with flow phenomena and physical alteration. *Applied Geochemistry*, 146, 105445.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeochem.2022.105445>

- Dhar, S., Naseri, M., Khawaja, H. A., Eirik, M. S., Edvardsen, K., Barabady, J. (2024). Sea-spray measurement tools and technique employed in marine icing field expeditions: A critical literature review and assessment using CFD simulations. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 217, 104029. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coldregions.2023.104029>.
- Ebrahim, A., Al-raoush, R. I., Seers, T. D. (2023). Clogging and permeability reduction dynamics in porous media: A numerical simulation study. *Powder Technology*, 427, 118736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2023.118736>
- Ferreira, T., Rasband, W. (2012). *ImageJ User Guide*. <https://imagej.net/ij/docs/guide/user-guide.pdf>
- Frippiat, C. C., Holeyman, A. E. A. (2008). Comparative review of upscaling methods for solute transport in heterogeneous porous media. *Journal of Hydrology*, 362, 150–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2021.117870>
- Guha, A. (2008). Transport and Deposition of Particles in Turbulent and Laminar Flow. *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, 40, 311–341. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.fluid.40.111406.102220>
- Hariti, Y., Hajji, Y., Hader, A., Faraji, H., Boughaleb, Y., Faraji, M., Saifaoui, D. (2020). Modelling of fluid flow in porous media and filtering water process: Langevin dynamics and Darcy's law based approach. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 30, 870–875. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.04.343>
- Leal, J., Avila, E. A., Darghan, A. E., Lobo, D. (2023). Spatial modeling of infiltration and its relationship with surface coverage of rock fragments and porosity in soils of an andean micro-watershed in Tolima (Colombia). *Geoderma Regional*, 33, e00637. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2023.e00637>
- Lee, J., Jung, H. (2022). Understanding the relationship between meltwater discharge and solute concentration by modeling solute transport in a snowpack in snow-dominated regions – A review. *Polar Science*, 31, 100782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polar.2021.100782>
- Li, H., Wang, S., Chen, X., Xie, L., Shao, B., Ma, Y. (2023). CFD-DEM simulation of aggregation and growth behaviors of fluid-flow-driven migrating particle in porous media. *Geoenergy Science and Engineering*, 231, 212343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoen.2023.212343>
- Lin, D., Hu, L., Bradford, S. A., Zhang, X., Lo, I. M. C. (2021). Pore-network modeling of colloid transport and retention considering surface deposition, hydrodynamic bridging, and straining. *Journal of Hydrology*, 603, 127020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.127020>
- Ling, X., Yan, Z., Liu, Y., Lu, G. (2021). Transport of nanoparticles in porous media and its effects on the co-existing pollutants. *Environmental Pollution*, 283, 117098. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.117098>
- McDowell-Boyer, L. M., Hunt, J. R., Sitar, N. (1986). Particle transport through porous media. *Water Resources Research*, 22(13), 1901–1921. <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1029/WR022i013p01901>

- Monga, R., Deb, R., Meyer, D. W., Jenny, P. (2023). A probabilistic, flux-conservative particle-based framework for transport in fractured porous media. *Advances in Water Resources*, 172, 104368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2023.104368>
- Nan, X., Liu, X., Wu, B., Zhang, H., Song, K., Wang, X. (2023). Coupled CFD-DEM simulation and experimental study of particle distribution and accumulation during tailings seepage process. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 427, 139229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139229>
- Nielsen, D.R., Hopmans, J.W., Kutílek, M., Wendroth, O. (1997). A brief review of soil water, solute transport and regionalized variable analysis. *Scientia Agricola*, 54, 89–115. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-90161997000300012>
- Nikon Metrology . (2015). X-Tek X-ray and CT Inspection CT Pro 3D for XT 6.10: User Manua IXTM0977-A1. 82p.
- Ren, W., Ershadnia, R., Wallace, C. D., Labolle, E. M., Dai, Z., Barros, F. P. J. de, Soltanian, M. R. (2022). Evaluating the Effects of Multiscale Heterogeneous Sediments on Solute Mixing and Effective Dispersion. *Water Resources Research*, 58(9), e2021WR031886. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021WR031886>
- Sadeghnejad, S., Enzmann, F., Kersten, M. (2022). Numerical Simulation of Particle Retention Mechanisms at the Sub-Pore Scale. *Transport in Porous Media*, 145, p. 127–151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11242-022-01843-y>
- Sahimi, M. (1995). *Flow and transport in porous media and fractured rock: from classical methods to modern approaches*. Weinheim ; New York: VCH.
- Silva, D. F. do N., Pérez, D. M., Proenza, Y. G., Carvalho, B. F. de, Rodríguez, A. G., & Antonino, A. C. D. (2024). Quantifying filter layer porosity: a comparative study of X-ray microtomography, fluid injection, and fluid saturation techniques. *Journal of Environmental Analysis and Progress*, 9(4), 356–368. <https://doi.org/10.24221/jeap.9.4.2024.7365.356-368>
- Spurin, C., Armstrong, R. T., McClure, J., Berg, S. (2023). Dynamic mode decomposition for analysing multi-phase flow in porous media. *Advances in Water Resources*, 175, 104423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2023.104423>
- Szilvsi-Nagy, M., Mátyási, G. (2003). Analysis of STL files. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, 38(7–9), 945–960. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0895-7177\(03\)90079-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0895-7177(03)90079-3)
- Tu, J., Yeoh, G. H., LIU, C. (2013). *Computational fluid dynamics: a practical approach*. 2nd ed. Amsterdam ; Boston: Elsevier/Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Wang, L., Cardenas, M. B., Wang, T., Zhou, J.-Q., Zheng, L., Chen, Y.-F., Chen, X. (2022). The effect of permeability on Darcy-to-Forchheimer flow transition. *Journal of Hydrology*, 610, 127836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2022.127836>
- White, Frank M (2009). *Fluid mechanics*. 6th ed. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.

Ye, X., Cui, R., Du, X., Ma, S. Zhao, J., Lu, Y., Wan, Y. (2019). Mechanism of Suspended Kaolinite Particle Clogging in Porous Media During Managed Aquifer Recharge. *Groundwater*, 57(5), 764–771. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gwat.12872>

Zheng, L., Lu, W., Wu, L., Zhou, Q. (2023). A review of integration between BIM and CFD for building outdoor environment simulation. *Building and Environment*, 228, 109862. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.109862>